

Medical and social aspects of the prevalence of road traffic injuries among children.

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Relevance of the topic

In recent years, road traffic accidents involving children and the resulting injuries, disabilities, and death rates have been growing, especially in middle and low-income countries [9], including our country, among the important medical, social, and organizational issues. One is counted. The seriousness of the problem is that injuries sustained in more than 10% of traffic accidents are a combination of many types of injuries. If 1.2 million people die in road traffic accidents every year, 20-50 million people are injured and disabled. It is noteworthy that more than half of those who died are aged 15-44. Road traffic accidents are the second leading cause of death among 5-14-year-olds and 15-29-year-olds. It is noted that traffic accidents among boys are 1.5 times higher than among girls. According to the WHO European Regional Bureau, death among children under the age of 20 due to traffic accidents is 5.24 per 100 car accidents in Belarus and ranks 9th among 47 countries. According to WHO, by 2030, traffic accidents are expected to become the fifth cause of death among children [1,2].

Research purpose

The current research focuses on studying, analyzing, and evaluating the literature and other scientific sources dedicated to the study of the causes of injuries, disabilities, and death among children in the countries of the world and also in our republic.

Methodology

Literature and other statistical materials and reports focused on the medical, social and organizational aspects of the causes of injury, disability and death among children due to marital injuries in the next 15-20 years in the world and in our country were taken as material for the research, and the descriptive method was widely used in the analysis of the literature. .

Results and discussion:

In recent years, domestic injuries and accidents among children have become one of the major medical, social and economic factors that threaten their lives and health. These conditions are the leading cause of death, especially among children over 3 years of age, even higher than those caused by infectious diseases, and in many cases cause disability and limit children's future career opportunities. It is noted that in many cases it directly depends on the architecture of the territory, settlement, types of transport and the level of organization of preventive measures. It should be noted that most children's injuries are injuries in marriage (55-60%). Half of all injuries to children occur when they are left unattended by an adult. The second place was occupied by school injuries (7-12%), and 3/4 of them occurred outside of school hours, and 1/3 of them occurred during the educational process. The third place is street injuries (3-4%), of which death is 8.4%, disability is 42.5%. Injuries in sports games make up -3-4%, in pre-school educational institutions -3-5%, it is noted that injuries are -2-2.5 times higher in boys aged 10-14 than in girls. It is noteworthy that 96% of injuries among preschoolers are domestic injuries, and they are mostly received at home. Domestic injuries in children under 3 years of age are 80%, and the number of street injuries in children after 7 years has increased [3,4].

S.G. Suvorov (2010) and T.M. According to the scientific conclusions of Andreeva et al. (2007), in Russia today, injuries due to road traffic accidents are considered a national tragedy and it is increasing. In 2009-2013, more than 226,000 people died and 1,430,000 people were

injured due to traffic accidents. [5,6] The main cause of traffic accidents in children in 40% of cases is non-observance of traffic rules, in 22% of cases - caused by alcohol consumption. The main part of children's injuries, i.e. 32.3% - on the street, in the courtyards of houses, 27% - at the crossings of the street, 17.9% - at home, 10.4% - at school, 6.1% - in auxiliary rooms, that is, it was found that they got it in fields, palaces, underground corridors, 3.5% - in forests, parks. Children received 3.9% of injuries at night, 9.6% in the morning, 34.1% in the afternoon, and 40.6% in the evening. The most dangerous period of children's injuries is considered to be in the evening, that is, from 17.00 to 21.00 (41.5%) [7]. According to the conclusion of A.A. Antonov (2019), in Russia, in 2016, compared to 2012, there was a slight decrease in traffic accidents among children. The author says that in 2012, 20,879 traffic accidents were recorded, resulting in 970 children's deaths and 22016 children's injuries. In 2016, this figure was 19,269, 710 and 20,621, respectively. According to the author, this situation is related to the introduction of serious changes to the traffic rules related to carrying children in cars at the state level [8]. More than 700,000 people die in car accidents in the WHO European region. At least 2,000 people die a day. More than 6,000 people will be hospitalized. More than 600,000 people seek emergency medical care due to injuries. Especially in middle and low-income countries, every 5/6 deaths are due to traffic accidents. In Kyrgyzstan, 90,000 people are admitted to hospitals each year due to injuries (per 100,000/876), more than 10,000 of which are children. According to the authors' data, 1041.8 cases per 100,000 children were recorded in Kyrgyzstan in 2014, of which 550.3 were domestic accidents, 258.1 were street accidents, 40.9 were traffic accidents, 61.9 - school, 35.1 - in sports, 95.5 - other various injuries, among which death was equal to -5.6 per 100,000 children. It is noteworthy that the number of traffic accidents, the number of injured people, and the number of deaths have been increasing in Kyrgyzstan during 2011-2015. [9]. It can be seen that over the next 15 years, the Russian Federation will take one of the leading places in terms of death from accidents among children and will be 20.0-29.9 per 100,000 children, which is 3-4 times higher than the Scandinavian countries (5.0-9, 9 / 100 00 children) [10]. According to the results of scientific studies carried out in Khabarovsk in 2018, most of the injuries recorded in children were recorded in boys, and it was found that it was high mainly in children aged 1-2 and 11-14. Types of reported cases 40.3% of children's injuries - on the street (ages 4-5 and 10-11), 30.5% - at home (ages 1-2), 14.5% - at schools (ages 11-14), 10.9% - in sports games, 1.6% - due to mutual quarrels, 2.1% - road traffic incidents [11].

In Russia, 12,000 injuries and poisonings are recorded per year, and 93% of them are injuries. This means that there are 120-130 injuries per 1000 inhabitants. This indicator is 100-110 in children, 160-170 among teenagers. It is noteworthy that all types of injuries, especially among children, have different indicators in different regions of the Russian Federation. For example, in 2018, injuries due to car accidents in the Chilabinsky region were every 100 142.8 cases per 000 inhabitants, in the Republic of Kalmyk it was equal to 258.5 cases, which was 76.7% higher than the average of the Russian Federation. According to the authors, similar peculiarities were observed in the rate of death from injuries, in Chilabinsk region it was equal to 14 4.7 per 100,000 population, while this indicator was equal to 116.6 on average for the country. [12].

According to the conclusion of V.N. Farafanova (2017) [13.14.], the main causes of injuries that occur among children in physical education classes are the organizational

deficiencies of these classes, the lack of technical safety indicators, the incorrect structure of training programs, the incorrect placement of equipment in halls and fields, the requirements of corridors not taking into account the age and gender characteristics of children, the absence of a teacher during the course of the lesson, incorrect situations in the teaching methodology, non-compliance with didactic principles, lack of individual approach to students during the course of the lesson, classes without taking into account their health, physical and technical preparation.

In many countries of the world, injury is the second leading cause of morbidity and mortality. It is especially alarming that this condition is common among growing young people and is increasing year by year. Every year, millions of children die due to injuries, and 13,000 of them occur in Russia. It causes 18-20% disability. [14]. The scientific conclusions of S.K. Nazarova and others (2016) indicate that all types of injuries are recorded more among boys (2/3). It is noted that four out of five occur during school breaks. According to the authors, the rate of injuries among children in Tashkent city has increased relatively (by 3.0%) and is 2.1 times higher than the average indicator of the Republic. In 2010-2014, injuries among children under 14 years of age in the Republic increased by 3.8% [15,16].

It is noted that 35-40% of injuries among school children are related to physical education classes: athletics, basketball, volleyball, football games. The causes of school injuries are divided into two groups: methodological and organizational. [16]. According to WHO data, more than 80 million accidents (injuries, falls, poisoning, burns, drowning) occur in European countries every year, and more than 500,000 people die. [17]. K.S. Soloveva, M.V. Martinova (2016) [18] According to the results of the scientific research carried out in the Nevsky district, a total of 23,420 cases were referred to the trauma department of the district polyclinic in 2014-2015. increased, 36.8% of them are on the street, 25.7% at home, 18% at school, 19.1% during sports games, 0.4% in vehicles and 10% in various other 52.3% of them were recorded in children aged 8-14 and 15-17, 40.0% of them were sprains, 15.2% were sprains, 9.1% were injuries, 3% - surface injuries, 5.7% - head injuries and concussions, 15.5% - bone fractures, 6.5% - leg fractures, 2.4% - spine and body injuries, 0, 1% were facial injuries and 4.5% were various other injuries.

According to Yu.N. Sosnovskaya (2018) [19], the most effective way to prevent injuries related to railway transport among children is the cooperation between the employees of the railway service and the employees of internal affairs, and it is scientifically based that it will give good results if it is implemented in the following ways: Determining the legal basis of mutual cooperation, establishing a joint coordinating body, developing a comprehensive program, exchanging information, ensuring the safety of each person, organizing joint events, making joint decisions, joint use of opportunities, joint meetings, organizing seminars and finally This includes discussing each incident together [19]. According to WHO's forward-looking estimates, by 2030, road traffic deaths will reach 2.4 million people and will rise from the ninth (2004) to the fifth leading cause of death. According to the report of the European region of WHO, Kazakhstan ranks first in terms of death from road traffic accidents. (30.6 per 100,000 population). It is noted that the Russian Federation takes the second place (25.2 per 100,000 inhabitants). In 2012, in the Shymkent region of Kazakhstan, it took the third place in terms of injuries in road traffic accidents, and it took the first place in terms of the cause of death among

the working population. As a result, the average life expectancy in the region decreased by -3.1-4.8 years for men and -1.2 years for women[20].

Traffic accidents account for a significant proportion of injuries among children, and children account for 5% of all road traffic deaths. Children's injuries account for 0.5-12.2% of all injuries. It is noted that the main injuries among children occur between 14:00 and 19:00. Injuries are typically higher among boys in most countries [21,22,23,25]. The main index of child health is injury and disability among children. In 2010, among children aged 0-14 in Russia, there were 10,705.2 injuries per 100,000 children. According to WHO, injuries are the leading cause of death among children worldwide. 950,000 children under the age of 18 die each year. This means that 100 children die every hour. According to the results of scientific research conducted in the Orenburg region, 47.5% of 107,857 treated children were injured on the street, 36.3% at home, 13.8% outside of school, and 2.1% at educational institutions. 44.2% of them fell from above, 18.7% - in living conditions and 1.4% - during sports games. [24]. Although injury among the population, especially among children, is a very serious problem of public health, society does not pay enough attention to this situation. Its causes require a multifaceted and complex approach. The positive solution of this problem requires the cooperation of dozens of institutions and organizations [26]. According to the scientific conclusions of E.G. Skryabin, A.G. Smirnikhs (2012) [27], 13.78% of injured persons are musculoskeletal system, 0.55% are spinal cord injuries. Spinal cord injuries mainly in 8-12-year-old children - 39.25%. Fracture of the vertebral body was 15.66%. Based on the information presented in the literature and scientific sources analyzed above, the following can be concluded.

1. From the literature and scientific sources on various types of injuries among children, it became known that among the total number of injuries among children, marital injuries take the leading place in almost many countries in terms of their prevalence;
2. Almost all identified and studied literature and scientific sources were mainly carried out abroad, including nomadic scientific research carried out in the Russian Federation and the Republic of Kazakhstan in separate regions. In our country, there were no scientific researches directed at marital injuries among children and carried out in the cross-section of separate regions together with its complex socio-hygienic, medical-social and organizational aspects;
3. Based on the study, it can be concluded that, taking into account the relative increase of various types of injuries among children, some specific characteristics of the population in terms of social, economic, and ethnic aspects, in the case of Khorezm region, marital injuries among children and its medical and social consequences and organizational aspects from a complex socio-hygienic point of view study and evaluation will have a good effect in improving the prevention of injuries among children.

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